

Optimization of Process Parameters and Multiscale Characterization of Nitinol Produced by Laser Powder Bed Fusion

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Abstract:

This study represents a comprehensive investigation of the relationship between the process parameters of laser powder bed fusion (L-PBF) technology and the specific properties of nitinol. Using wide range of laser powers (40-400 W) and scanning speeds (175-3000 mm·s⁻¹), the most promising parameter combinations are selected for production of bulk specimens, metamaterial segments and walls in different thicknesses between 0.5 and 2 mm. Porosity, dimensional accuracy, crystallography, austenite-martensite phase transformation and mechanical properties are investigated. The results show that with a volumetric energy density (*VED*) of 41-55 J·mm⁻³, a porosity of less than 0.3 % can be achieved, although after manufacturing brittle cracking may occur. Phase transformation measurements show single exothermic and endothermic peaks with austenite finish temperature below room temperature for all tested configurations, resulting in superelastic behavior without noticeable temperature-induced shape memory. Cyclic compression tests show a variable quasilinear pseudoelasticity with low hysteresis. The highest total strain after 50 cycles is 5.46 % with an associated cumulative residual strain of 2.79 %. The deterioration in recovery strain is significant during the initial phase of cyclic

loading and stabilized after approximately 30 cycles. Transmission Kikuchi diffraction (TKD) confirms fine martensite laths embedded in deformation bands, indicating high dislocation density.

PREPRINT VERSION

1. Introduction

Nickel-titanium alloys become of great interest for high-end biomedical and aerospace applications due to their unique ability to undergo large deformations (up to 8~10 %) and return to their original, undeformed shape.^[1,2] Recoverability is achieved either by the application of heat, referred to as shape memory effect (SME), or by the release of stress, so-called superelastic effect (SE). The SME/SE are enabled by a reversible phase transformation between the austenitic phase B2 (A) and the martensitic phase B19' (M).^[3,4] Both effects enable a reversible change in the shape of the component and thus open up the possibility of developing artificial actuators and more flexible components.

The latest development has taken advantage of the properties of nitinol and targets internally structured single-component actuators as a highly reliable replacement for complex mechanisms, such as those found in the leading and trailing edges of aircraft wings or highly flexible components in payload separation systems.^[5] To use them in real applications, a large actuation range has to be achieved in a relatively stiff component without damaging it, which until recently was considered impossible.^[6,7] However, the progressive development of additive manufacturing processes, such as laser powder bed fusion (L-PBF), has enabled the direct fabrication of nitinol metamaterials, where the specific geometry and thermomechanical behavior can be tailored to the desired functionality.^[8] Topology optimization methods can be used to optimize the internal geometry while the thermomechanical response of the material can be tuned by the L-PBF process parameters and heat treatment.

Apart from the thermomechanical behavior, the processing parameters play an essential role in the formation of porosity, microstructure formation and phase transformation temperatures.^[9,10] Previous studies have shown that even different combinations of laser power and scanning speed at the same energy density led to different material performance.^[11] The influence of laser power on nickel content in a molten pool is particularly pronounced due to the risk of evaporation at high temperatures, which can be avoided by the reduction of energy input via increased scanning speed.^[12] In addition, the surface quality of a build is significantly influenced by the scanning speed to laser power ratio.^[10] The ratio values higher than 0.3 or lower than 0.1 results in a considerable number of spherical pores.^[13] In contrast, the L-PBF fabrication of thin-walled nitinol parts has shown favorable results in achieving higher geometric accuracy with lower scanning speeds, especially in the case of parts with small struts (0.2 mm - 0.6 mm).^[14]

Post-processing, such as heat treatment, has also a major influence on the nitinol functional properties. The precipitation characteristics are highly dependent on the aging temperature and dwell time, cooling rate and other alloying elements.^[15] The study of Rao et al. indicated that the actuating performance of a nitinol shape memory alloy (SMA) beam actuator improved with increasing heat treatment temperature.^[5] For nitinol produced with L-PBF, Saedi et al. showed that the specimens aged at 350°C for 18 hours exhibited near ideal superelasticity with 5.5% strain recovery and only 0.3% unrecoverable strain at the first cycle under a load of 1000 MPa.^[15] Aging heat treatment leads to precipitation hardening that is not related to the matrix phase. As a result, higher phase transformation temperatures can be achieved compared to conventionally produced nitinol, which forms coherent precipitates after aging.^[16] This affects the response to mechanical loading in ambient temperature which is crucial in real applications.^[17]

In general, L-PBF processed nitinol microstructure consist mainly of austenite and a small amount of martensite at room temperature.^[18] The phase transformation temperatures of L-PBF processed structure are higher than of powder precursor due to nickel evaporation during the L-PBF process.^[8,15] With respect to metamaterial applications, Iasnii et al. have shown that the termination temperature of austenitic transformation in nitinol bulk rods is much lower compared to those of thin struts in lattice structures.^[19] In addition, Zhang et al. found that elastic modulus deteriorated and residual strain increased while applied maximum strain was increased.^[20] Particularly affected are starting temperature of the forward martensitic transformation M_s under compressive loading and termination temperature of the martensitic transformation A_f during unloading.

Load history is another important factor to consider when developing aerospace components, as recoverability decreases with the number of load cycles.^[11,21] According to Saedi et al., the superelastic behavior of nitinol specimens fabricated with L-PBF can be considered stabilized after the 10th cycle.^[15] In contrast, Henderson et al. found stabilization up to the 40th cycle.^[17] According to Chen et al., nitinol gradient lattice structures achieved a recoverable displacement rate of at least 99.15% after six cycles.^[22] This resulted in performance inconsistency in nitinols fabricated by L-PBF with different process parameters. Further investigation of cyclic tensile loading with increasing loads and conventional stress-controlled fatigue showed that the higher proportion of retained martensite reduces fatigue life.^[23] In addition, an increase in residual strain and a decrease in the elastic modulus can be observed when the maximum compressive strain increases under cyclic loading.^[20]

Regardless of the application, efficient development of internally structured actuators with tailored mechanical behavior requires a deep understanding of the relationship between phenomenological behavior of nitinol L-PBF process parameters, obtained microstructure, and resulting mechanical properties. This relationship can be interpreted based on material and geometry characteristics determined for a specific thin-walled production setup. Unfortunately, not much attention has been paid to the complex consideration of the relationship between the L-PBF manufacturing parameters and the resulting functional properties in relation to thin-walled components. This study addresses the lack of knowledge about the relationship between process parameters and the mechanical behavior of nitinol. A group of potentially effective process parameters were identified and further investigated with respect to thermal, mechanical and geometrical aspects. The study provides an experimentally sound, production-specific description of nitinol behavior and forms a solid basis for the development of internally structured components with an elasticity that goes beyond the limits of conventional metallic materials.

2. Materials and methods

The aim of this study was to obtain an experimental description of the fabrication-specific thermomechanical behavior of a nitinol alloy produced by L-PBF. The following section describes the main analyzes carried out from the process parameters development towards the detection of the austenite-martensite phase transformation limit.

2.1 Powder characteristics

Gas atomized nitinol metal powder (Carpenter Additive, Widnes, United Kingdom) was selected for the manufacturing of the specimen. The shape of the particles was analyzed using a scanning electron microscope (SEM, **Table 1**). The particle size distribution was determined by laser size diffraction using the ASTM B822 standard. The tap density of the powder was determined to be $4.26 \text{ kg}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$ using the ASTM B527 standard. The chemical powder composition of the nitinol alloy is given in **Table 2**.

Table 1 – Size distribution of nitinol powder; nitinol powder morphology – SEM image.

Quantile	Particle size [μm]
Q_{10}	13.3
Q_{50}	30
Q_{90}	51.2

Table 2 – Chemical composition of nitinol powder.

	Ni	C	Cr	Co	Cu	H
wt. %	55.75	0.0024	0.0042	<0.001	<0.0035	<0.0005
	Fe	Nb	N	O	Ti	
wt. %	0.0044	<0.001	<0.0005	0.058	Bal.	

2.2 Production of nitinol specimens

The specimens were produced using an SLM 280HL machine (SLM Solutions Group AG, Lübeck, Germany). An ytterbium Gaussian-mode fiber laser YLR-400-WC-Y11 (IPG Photonics, Oxford, USA) with 400 W maximum power, a spot diameter of 82 μm and a wavelength of 1070 nm was used. A reduced 100 \times 100 mm nitinol base plate and a standard silicone recoater blade were used to produce specimens. **Table 3** gives an overview of the initial process parameters used.

Table 3 – The L-PBF machine process parameters.

Laser Power P [W]	Borders	40-400
	Fill Contours	150
	Hatching	40-400
Scanning speed V [$\text{mm}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$]	Borders	175-3000
	Fill Contours	450
	Hatching	175-3000
Hatch distance H [μm]		75-125
Layer thickness L [μm]		50
Scanning strategy [-]		Bidirectional hatching (stripes)
Interlayer orientation [$^\circ$]		67
Platform heating [$^\circ\text{C}$]		200
Atmosphere [-]		Ar
Residual oxygen content [%]		<0.2

The following equation was used to determine the volumetric thermal energy density (VED) delivered to the powder layer during the manufacturing process:

$$VED = \frac{P}{V \cdot H \cdot L} \quad [\text{J} \cdot \text{mm}^{-3}] \quad (1)$$

where P is the laser power, V denotes the laser speed, H represents the hatch spacing and L refers to the layer thickness.

Table 4 shows the types and geometric parameters of the test specimens produced in each group. The cylinders were fabricated to represent the uniaxial stress-strain state in the bulk nitinol material, while the walls were fabricated to represent the geometric features of a thin element, similar to those found in planar metamaterials. Three different configurations of metamaterial segments were produced (**Figure 1**), two of which were designed with slight auxetic behavior. The geometries frequently used in other studies for conventionally produced materials were chosen intentionally for better comparison.^[24,25]

Table 4 – Types and geometric parameters of the test specimens.

	Height [mm]	Diameter/Thickness [mm]
Bulk cylinder	10	8
Thin wall	10	0.5;0.75;1;1.25;1.5;2
Metamaterial segments	10	0.5; 0.75

Figure 1 – Basic element and metamaterial segment: (a), (b) re-entrant; (c), (d) arrowhead; (e), (f) honeycomb.

2.3 Microscope image analysis

The Keyence VHX-2500 digital microscope (Keyence, Osaka, Japan) with the Z250R objective (x250 zoom) was used to obtain detailed information on the cross-sectional geometry and porosity of the specimens. The microscope images of the specimen cross-sections were analyzed using the plugin of the Java Script based open-source software ImageJ2 Fiji (National Institutes of Health, Bethesda, Maryland, USA). Images were converted to greyscale with a range of 0-255 (0-white, 255-black) to detect pores and borders. Then the threshold filter was applied to select a range of 110-255. In this way, the images were transferred into binary maps in which the porosity and dimensions of specimens were recognized based on binary criteria.

2.4 Material composition analysis

A combination of SEM and energy dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS) was used to compare the changes in material composition, in particular the amount of nickel evaporated during the L-PBF process. The SEM examination was performed with the Zeiss Ultra-Plus 50 (Carl Zeiss AG, Oberkochen, Germany). Chemical composition analysis was carried out using the EDS detector (Oxford Instruments, High Wycombe, United Kingdom).

Microstructure characterization was performed on the specimens extracted from tested specimens to observe initial and deformed microstructure. The cross-sections were mechanically ground by SiC papers followed by electrolytic polishing to achieve high surface quality for electron back-scattered diffraction (EBSD). The microstructural characterization was conducted using a TESCAN LYRA 3 XMU field emission gun scanning electron microscope (SEM) equipped with an Oxford Instruments Symmetry EBSD detector. The acquired raw EBSD data were processed by the AZtecCrystal software (Oxford Instruments, United Kingdom).

X-ray diffraction (XRD) measurements on powders and sintered samples were carried out by the Empyrean X-ray diffractometer (Malvern Panalytical, Worcestershire, UK). The diffraction patterns were measured from 10° to 130° (2θ) with the Co $K\alpha$. The phase composition of the samples was quantified using the Rietveld analysis (HighScore Plus, Malvern Panalytical, UK).

2.5 Transformation temperatures

The transformation temperatures of nitinol produced from L-PBF were determined using differential scanning calorimetry (DSC). For this purpose, specimens with the dimensions $4 \times 4 \times 1 \text{ mm}^3$ were cut from the bulk material cylinders using the electrical discharge machining (EDM) method. The NETZSCH DSC 204 F1 Phoenix device (Erich Netzsch GmbH & Co. Holding KG, Selb, Germany) with intercooler was used for the DSC analysis. Each specimen was placed in the aluminum crucible with a lid and subjected to three temperature cycles ranging from 75°C to -75°C at constant heating and cooling rate of $10 \text{ K}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$. The test was performed in an argon atmosphere with flow rate of $70 \text{ ml}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$, as its lower thermal conductivity increases the sensitivity in the low temperature range. An empty aluminum crucible with lid served as reference material. The temperature was calibrated to the melting temperature of five various pure substances. The NETZSCH Proteus® program was used to evaluate acquired DSC data.

2.6 Mechanical properties

The mechanical properties were determined using a cyclic compression test on a Shimadzu AGX-V2 device (Shimadzu, Kjóto, Japan). In the first phase, the cylindrical specimens described in Section 2.2 were compressed in the direction parallel to the build direction (BD) until intermediate load level of 800 MPa of engineering stress was reached, and then unloaded (the L-PBF fabricated nitinol should not reach the plastic yield point), as shown in **Table 5**. In this condition, 50 loading cycles were performed at a load rate of approximately $2 \text{ kN}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$.^[8,16] In the second phase, a further 25 cycles of high stress were carried out, which were increased by five load cycles up to 1200 MPa. The mechanical testing was carried out at room temperature, assuming superelastic behavior with no signs of thermally induced austenite-martensite phase transformation.

The deformation of the specimens was recorded with an optical extensometer (Dantec Dynamics, Skovlunde, Denmark), which is based on the principle of digital 3D image correlation (DIC) and works with two 5 MPx cameras. The setup covered a measurement area of approx. $25 \times 25 \text{ mm}$ (base length 97.6 mm, stereo angle 27.26°). To cover the range, the system used 50 mm lenses with 10 mm intermediate rings. A customized imaging technique was used to reduce the acquired data. The correlation parameters are listed in Table 5.

Table 5 – DIC correlation parameters; applied test parameters with time steps.

Searching radius	148 Px
Facet size	31
Grid spacing	17 Px
Maximum 3D residuum	0.6 Px

In addition, metamaterial segments were tested with the same facility. Specimens were freely placed between plates and 10 times compressed in direction perpendicular to BD. The testing conditions are shown in the **Figure 2** (a), where applied displacement u_y from diagram in the Figure 2 (b) was used.

Figure 2 – (a) Loading scene used in the simulation; (b) loading diagram.

2.7 Finite element analysis

The FEA of the metamaterial segments was performed in ANSYS Workbench 23.1. (ANSYS, Canonsburg, Pennsylvania, USA) in the Static Structural module. The simulation scene was created to correspond to Figure 2 (a) with assumption of plane stress conditions. Applied displacement uy was overtaken from Figure 2 (b). The planar 8-node elements with quadratic base function, referred to as PLANE 183, were used with a side length of 0.1 mm to mesh the segment and plates. A mesh convergence study was performed to ensure that further mesh refinement would not impact the accuracy of the results. Rounding in corners and sharp edges of geometry were created to represent actual state of segments after production. Friction between bodies was set to 0.5. Poisson's ratio was set to 0.3. A linear elastic material assumption was adopted based on compression test of cylinders with modulus of elasticity determined for each loading loop separately.

3. Results and discussion

3.1 Process parameters development

In the first step, the process parameter window defined in section 2.2 was tested experimentally in the form of single tracks. The track properties were acquired as discrete results of 90 microscopic measurements of track width W , height H , depth D and contact angle α (**Figure A. 1**). As expected, a decrease in scanning speed V and an increase in laser power P led to an increase in W , D and in some cases α , while H decreases. A similar trend with close match at intermediate scanning speeds was also observed in the study by Bourke et al. in a narrower process parameter window.^[26]

A regression analysis using a quadratic polynomial function was performed to determine the relationship between the input process parameters and the resulting track properties, similar to Vaglio et al.^[27] Equation 2 represents the trend of approximated track properties (Z with $Z \in \{W, H, D, \alpha\}$) as a function of change in scan velocity (V) in $\text{mm}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$ and laser power (P) in W. In addition, a continuous prediction of track properties was made based on possible combinations of input parameters. The polynomial parameters of the regression function ($\beta_0 \dots \beta_5$) are given in the **Table A. 1**. From this it can be concluded that a better approximation and thus a potential trend prediction was achieved for the track width and depth due to the relatively low mean square error. The poorer approximation of the track height can be attributed to the wide window of process parameters, which in extreme cases led to considerable melt pool pulsations and a balling effect, which is reflected in a greater variation of the track height. Large variations in the measured height led to a deviation from the plane that approximates the data set, even when a second-order polynomial function was used. Based on the observed track

continuity, uniformity, absence of cracks and the dimensions mentioned above, 12 groups of process parameters were selected for further investigation of bulk specimens (**Figure A. 2**).

$$Z = \beta_0 + \beta_1 V + \beta_2 P + \beta_3 V^2 + \beta_4 P^2 + \beta_5 VP \quad (2)$$

3.2 Bulk material analysis

The analysis of the internal porosity of the bulk specimens showed low values overall (**Figure 3 (a)**). It increased to a maximum value of 0.37 % for V at an intermediate value of $1000 \text{ mm} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$, $P = 400 \text{ W}$ and a high value of $H = 125 \mu\text{m}$, resulting in a peak VED of $64 \text{ J} \cdot \text{mm}^{-3}$. When the filter was applied to the sum of pores with an area of at least $10 \mu\text{m}^2$, a significantly lower maximum porosity of 0.24 % was observed. In contrast, the lowest unfiltered and filtered porosity of less than 0.1 % each was achieved when H was reduced to $105 \mu\text{m}$ and P to 280 W , resulting in a VED of $53.3 \text{ J} \cdot \text{mm}^{-3}$. The comparison of the maximum and minimum porosity resulted in the same values for the specimens regardless of filtering. The more comprehensive comparison with review literature, in which different process parameters and Ni contents were taken into account, resulted in a higher relative density of the material.^[28,29] The only comparable density was obtained with a VED of $41 \text{ J} \cdot \text{mm}^{-3}$ with a similar Ni content and similar parameters.^[30] In general, a very high relative density for VED in the range of $41\text{-}55 \text{ J} \cdot \text{mm}^{-3}$ was achieved in and in the present study, with a porosity of less than 0.3 %. However, it is worth noting that the layer thickness used in the source study was only $30 \mu\text{m}$.

Unfortunately, some of the specimens with the highest relative density were prone to macroscopic cracking after fabrication (**Figure 3 (a) detail**), which is why the process parameters combinations used for their fabrication were not investigated further. Macroscopic cracking of cylindrical specimens has also been described in the literature for process parameters that resulted in approximately equal VED values.^[29]

Figure 3 – (a) Comparison of the porosity of bulk specimens; (b) change in atomic content as a function of the L-PBF process parameters.

The EDS measurement results showed how the concentration of individual chemical elements changed when the material was subjected to the laser fusion process. Due to the very low concentration, some of the chemical elements were excluded from the comparison as their occurrence was negligible. Figure 3 (b) compares the average measured atomic content of nickel in the alloy processed with L-PBF with the concentration in the initial state. Due to the lower melting point temperature of nickel, its content in nitinol can decrease during the manufacturing process.^[31] As a result, nickel evaporation can lead to a shift in transformation temperatures. However, despite the small variations in nickel content within the observed range, no significant decrease was observed with increasing *VED*. This was confirmed by the standard deviation in the graph, which overlaps with the nickel content in the premanufacturing state. According to Zhan et al., a significant decrease in nickel content would require a *VED* value of over $65 \text{ J}\cdot\text{mm}^{-3}$.^[32] The authors of the study used a *VED* value of about $87 \text{ J}\cdot\text{mm}^{-3}$ with remelting to adjust the transformation temperatures and achieve adequate performance of mechanical properties. The observed increase in Ni content at a *VED* of about $45 \text{ J}\cdot\text{mm}^{-3}$ could be explained by the proximity to the detection limit of the EDS analyses.^[33]

3.3 Thin walls analysis

Of the 12 remaining groups of process parameters, the 3 most promising (**Table 6**), characterized by low porosity and the absence of cracks in the manufactured specimens, were selected for further investigation in the form of thin-walls with a nominal thickness of 0.5-2 mm. **Figure 4** (a) shows a 0.5 mm thick specimen with a measured mean thickness below the nominal value, while Figure 4 (b) shows a 2 mm thick specimen with a mean thickness above the nominal value. The range of the measured data in Figure 4 (b), expressed by three times the standard deviation, was significantly larger than that of the data in Figure 4 (a), indicating that the variation in manufacturing dimensions increased when higher nominal thicknesses were used.

Table 6 – Process parameters for bulk material cylinders and thin walls.

Group		A	B	C
VED [$\text{J}\cdot\text{mm}^{-3}$]		43	60	50
Laser Power P [W]	Borders	200	280	360
	Fill Contours	150	150	150
	Hatching	200	280	360

Scanning speed V [$\text{mm}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$]	Borders	1250	750	1250
	Fill Contours	450	450	450
	Hatching	1250	750	1250
Hatch distance H [μm]		90	125	115

Figure 4 – Dimensional analysis of the thin wall of (a) group A with a nominal thickness of 0.5 mm; (b) group C with a nominal thickness of 2 mm.

Figure 5 shows the overall comparison of the mean measured thicknesses compared to the nominal values. It can be clearly seen that the measured specimens tended to be thinner at a nominal value of 0.5 mm, regardless of the group. The lowest measured thickness was observed for group B with a mean value of 465 μm . With this exception, the measured thickness was greater than the nominal thickness. The largest thickness deviation was measured at 2 mm nominal thickness with a maximum value of 2148 μm for group C (Figure 5 (a)). On the other hand, the smallest thickness deviations were found for group A across the entire range of nominal thicknesses tested. It is worth noting that the threefold standard deviation of the measured thickness does not overlap with the nominal thickness at 1.5 mm and 2 mm. Surprisingly, thicker walls led to larger deviations, but these were more uniform in thickness variation. The mechanism responsible for the different wall thickness deviations in the different groups could be attributed to the different energy density supplied to the melt pool, as well as the lower heat dissipation path for thinner walls.^[34,35] A higher temperature of the melt pools can be expected with them, which leads to a lower number of adhering particles. As a result, thicker walls tended to have greater thickness due to the larger number of adhering particles.

Another parameter that played a key role here was the scanning strategy, which influenced the mutual position of the contours and the scan vectors used for the core hatching.^[36,37] In addition, as a result of the sliced geometry, some of the very short vectors could be omitted when the laser passed the scan path, especially in the case of very thin walls.

Figure 5 – (a) Measured wall thickness (error bars represent triple standard deviations); (b) porosity of the walls including the number of pores for a pore size $\geq 10\mu\text{m}^2$ – columns without hatching.

The porosity for thin walls produced with the above-mentioned groups of process parameters is shown in Figure 5 (b). It represents the total porosity found, while the number of pores in the same figure shows the porosity as the sum of the pores found, filtered by pores with an area of $10\mu\text{m}^2$ or more. Looking at the unfiltered data of all groups, it can be assumed that a higher porosity can be observed for thin walls with a lower nominal thickness. Porosity reached 1.68 % for group A and a nominal thickness of 0.5 mm and decreased irregularly with increasing nominal wall thickness. An approximately similar trend can also be observed for groups B and C, indicating that the influence of subsurface porosity is particularly high for thin specimens. One possible cause could be the heat dissipation in the built direction, which was dominant. In consequence, the melt pool became deeper with decreasing thickness and promoted the formation of keyhole pores, leading to increased porosity.^[34] In general, the pores in this experiment occurred in chains in subsurface areas at all heights (Figure 5 (b) violet arrows). This effect was attributed to the increased evaporation of metal because of changes in scan

velocity during the slowdown of the laser spot reversal at the end of each track.^[38] For thin walls, where very short hatch tracks were generated, this effect was even more detrimental.

3.4 Phase transformation behavior

Figure 6 (a) showed the first cycle of the DSC measurement on selected specimens in as-built condition. The heating of the specimen to +75 °C and the subsequent cooling to -75 °C cause an endothermic and an exothermic peak in the curve. During the forward transformation from austenite to martensite, the corresponding exothermic peak indicated a direct single step transformation without the occurrence of the R-phase.^[15,39] The heating curve also showed a reverse single step transformation indicated by the endothermic peak. It should be noted that the exothermic peak occurred at the edge of the measured temperature interval, which made it impossible to estimate the end of the martensitic transformation. The broad and flat shape of the curve indicates a slow and weak transformation, which is probably the result of the L-PBF process producing a high dislocation density in as-built state.

Figure 6 (b) showed the characteristic temperatures A_s , A_p and A_f (start, peak and end of austenite transformation during heating) as well as M_s and M_p (start and end of martensite formation during cooling) in comparison to the initial state of the powder. The powder material showed a purely superelastic behavior at conditions far above room temperature (at 41 °C). In contrast, all configurations produced at room temperature can be considered superelastic, as the endothermic reaction A_f ended below 20 °C. Accordingly, a comparison of the martensitic transformation of the as-built specimen showed that the onset of the exothermic reaction in the group A and group C configurations began at lower M_s temperatures. According to the EDS measurement (Figure 3 (b)), these groups were the configurations in which a slight decrease in Ni was measured after processing. This finding contradicts the literature, which reported an increase in phase transformation temperature in a certain range when nickel evaporated.^[33,40] However, it should be noted that the change in nickel content measured in this study was below the standard deviation due to the lower input energies, so no further conclusions can be drawn. It can also be concluded from Figure 6 and Table 6 that a lower scanning speed leads to higher transformation temperatures.

Figure 6 – (a) DSC curves of selected specimens showing change in transformation temperatures as a function of the L-PBF processing parameters; (b) summarized phase transformation temperatures compared to the values applicable to the powder (dashed lines).

3.5 Compression test

The first phase of the cyclic compression result of the bulk material cylinders subjected to a maximum compressive stress of 800 MPa at each loading cycle showed a variable superelastic response with the highest total strain of 5.43 % at the 50th cycle for group B (**Figure 7**), while the lowest total strain was observed for group C at only 4.65 %. The most significant decrease in recoverability is observed in group B, where the cumulative residual strain reaches 2.79 % after 50 cycles. A comparison with additively manufactured nitinol specimens described in the literature and tested under similar conditions showed that group B achieves a similar stiffness to but a lower stiffness than, resulting in a higher total strain at maximum load at the 50th cycle.^[41,42] No plateau region was observed in the loading loops, but as the number of loading cycles increases, the loop shape narrowed to a quasilinear pseudoelasticity with little hysteresis. According to Liu et al., one possible reason for this is the nanocrystalline/amorphous dual-phase structure that occurred in mechanically cyclized L-PBF fabricated nitinol.^[43] Furthermore, it is reported in the study that an increase in scanning speed, which resulted in deformation of the melt pool, led to a reduction in the transformation temperature and an increase in the transformation interval. This is also confirmed in the current study, where a decrease in transformation temperature was observed for groups A and C at higher scanning speed (from 750 mm/s for B to 1250 mm/s). Another study indicated that the build orientation of the tested specimen also plays an important role in hysteresis and superelastic recovery.^[44]

Figure 7 – Stress-strain curves of superelastic nitinol at 50 cycles.

In all specimen groups observed, the deterioration in recovery and the rapid change in hysteresis were most pronounced in the first cycles, leading to a narrowing of the loop until the difference between the loading and unloading pathways almost disappeared (Figure 7). Similar behavior was also observed by other researchers, indicating a limitation of additively manufactured nitinol for applications with large repeating deformations.^[18,37] According to recent studies, the increase in unrecoverable strain is attributed to an increasing number of structural dislocations sliding as a result of mechanical loading of low yield strength nitinol produced from L-PBF.^[8] In addition, the quasi-linear superelastic response indicated no obvious change in crystal structures. The most likely reason for this is the increase in dislocation density due to functional fatigue, which changed strong first-order transition to weak first-order or continuous transition.^[39,40] Clarification of the underlying mechanisms for this type of behavior plays an important role in the development of programmable metamaterials.

Figure 8 (a) shows the maximum total strain (ϵ_{tot}) and the cumulative residual strain (ϵ_{res}) for the individual groups of specimens tested. The load loops were considered stabilized if at least five adjacent cumulative residual strains showed a difference of less than 0.01%. According to this criterion, the observed trend of material recovery showed stabilization at 38th cycle for groups A and B and stabilization at 36th cycle for group C. This was consistent with the results described in a previous study where stabilization was observed between the 30th and 40th cycle for conventionally produced nitinol wires.^[17] In contrast, in another source study, stabilization of nitinol produced by selective laser melting in the as-fabricated state was observed as early as the 10th cycle.^[15]

Figure 8 – (a) Maximum total and cumulative residual strain in relation to the initial height at 50 cycles with 40 kN; (b) Maximum total and cumulative residual strain in relation to the initial height at a further 25 cycles with increased load.

However, it is important to emphasize that the cyclic test in the source study was terminated after the 10th cycle and the stabilization criterion differs from the current study. Despite the difference in the recognition of stabilization, the recoverable strain at the 10th cycle was in the range of 2.34 % and 2.9 %, which is comparable to the source study.

Further observations showed that additional cyclic loading led to a slow deterioration of nitinol in the form of a continuous reduction in recovery and a hysteresis to the quasilinear form. It was measurable in all tested groups regardless of the process parameters used until the last experimentally tested cycle. The recovery ratio can be used as an indicator (Figure 8 (a)), expressed as the ratio between the cumulative residual strain and the maximum total strain in percent.^[11] Group C achieved the highest recovery ratio with 82.4 % in the 1st cycle and 53.4 % in the 50th cycle. Similar behavior, including the reduction in hysteresis, was also observed in previous studies testing conventionally manufactured nitinol wires.^[21,45] However, it appeared that fewer loading cycles were required to achieve a significant reduction in hysteresis and recovery in specimens prepared with L-PBF.^[11] The offset in stabilized values of recovery strain between the tested groups in the first phase at intermediate load with 800 MPa engineering stress is attributed to different process parameters (Table 6) and is associated with a slight change in transformation temperatures between all groups. A possible mechanism for this phenomenon remains to be investigated in detail before a comprehensive conclusion can be drawn.

The second test phase with increased maximum load (Figure 8 (b)) showed a persistent trend of increasing cumulative residual strain in the unloaded state, indicating continued degradation

of the material with no obvious change in behavior. It is worth noting that both the maximum total strain achieved, and the cumulative residual strain measured at the corresponding loading intervals increased more rapidly, with the trend being amplified at the higher loads. In this respect, group B proved to be the most affected by the higher loads, as it reached the highest level of maximum total strain of 10.3 % at 1 200 MPa but is also the most prone to deterioration (cumulative residual strain of 7.0 %). At intermediate load, the offset in recoverable strain between the tested groups remained the same in the later stages of loading. As the load increased to a high level, the difference in recoverable strain decreased, stabilized the offset between groups. Interestingly, the recovery ratio of group B dropped to 31.6 %, which was the same level as group A. Although group C had the lowest maximum total strain, its recovery ratio was better in both phases of the test. This indicates that the recovery ratio depends on the load that and the offset between the recoverable strains of different groups is mitigated at high loads. This implies that for engineering applications, stabilization at the intended load must be performed before commissioning L-PBF fabricated components for service and that a limited number of cycles can be expected.

3.6 Microstructural characterization

The inverse pole figure (IPF) color-coded EBSD maps (see **Figure 9** (a) and (c)) showed as-built structure in cross-sections along and perpendicular to BD. The structure reflected highly directional solidification and grain growth, resulting in a significantly textured microstructure with elongated columnar grains. This phenomenon stemmed from steep thermal gradients during the layer-by-layer melting process, where grains grow and solidify perpendicular to the pool boundary towards the centerline of the melt pool.^[46-48] This was also reflected in complex and irregular grain morphology. Corresponding pole figures (Figure 9 (e)) confirmed a pronounced {100} texture along the BD, which was frequently reported for alloys with cubic-centered crystal lattices produced by L-PBF.^[49] This crystallographic texture is known to influence the anisotropic mechanical and functional properties of nitinol, including the orientation dependence of the martensitic transformation and the superelastic behavior of the alloy.

The IPF shows a section perpendicular to the BD in which the grain boundaries correspond to the orientation angle of the interlayer paths of 67° (Figure 9 (d)). The figure shows wrinkled grain boundaries in contrast to conventionally produced nitinol, which crystallizes directly from the melt pool.^[50,51]

Figure 9 – Observation of nitinol specimen of group C in as-built state: (a) IPF Y – crystallographic grain orientation in the BD; (b) band contrast map in the BD; (c) IPF Z – crystallographic grain orientation in the plane perpendicular to the BD; (d) band contrast map in the plane perpendicular to the BD; (e) volume fraction distribution of austenite.

The comparison of the as-built microstructure (Figure 9) and after cyclic loading (**Figure 10**) illustrated distinct changes. The originally columnar grains appeared fragmented, with signs of grain subdivision and increased intragranular misorientation. These changes indicated the accumulation of plastic strains and stress-induced martensitic transformation (SIMT).^[52,53] The columnar grain structure remained partially visible but is disrupted by the formation of subgrains and deformation bands. Interestingly, some of the grains did not tend to have deformation bands, while somewhere bands were present across several neighboring grains (Figure 10 (b) and (e)). This increased heterogeneity in crystallographic orientation indicates strain localization and dislocation activity typical of nitinol under cyclic strain.^[54,55] Phase analysis revealed localized martensitic transformations within deformation bands (Figure 10 (c) and (f)) characterized by strong local misorientation and disturbed crystallographic alignment, which act as preferential sites for SIMT. The strong granular texture indicated by the intensity peak in the {100} in Figure 9 (e) was not confirmed after cyclic loading. Instead, weaker, more diffuse intensities can be observed in all directions.

The transmission Kikuchi diffraction (TKD) map (**Figure 11**) confirmed fine martensite laths embedded in deformation bands. Variants of B19' martensite can be recognized by their

different orientations, which depend on orientation of particular grain with respect to loading direction. Moreover, a band contrast map (Figure 11 (b)) indicated that deformation bands contained high dislocation density. The presence of residual martensite in these areas indicated a partial irreversibility of the transformation process, which is consistent with functional fatigue mechanisms such as transformation-induced plasticity and dislocation locking.^[54] Such microstructural evolution was closely related to the degradation of superelastic performance, as described in Section 3.5.

Figure 10 – Observation of nitinol specimens of group C after cyclic loading: (a) IPF Y – crystallographic grain orientation in the BD; (b) IPF Y – magnification of the deformation bands; (c) band contrast map in the BD; (d) IPF Z – crystallographic grain orientation in the plane perpendicular to the BD; (e) IPF Z – magnification of the deformation bands; (f) band contrast map in the plane perpendicular to the BD; (g) volume fraction distribution of B2.

Figure 11 – TKD of nitinol specimen of group C after cyclic loading: (a) IPF X – crystallographic grain orientation in the BD; (b) band contrast map; (c) phase map (red – B2 austenite, blue – B19' martensite).

The quantification of the phases by X-ray diffraction (XRD) supported microstructural observations. After cyclic loading, a significant reduction in the B2 austenite phase fraction from 97.7 % to 91.5 % and an increase in B19' martensite from 2.3 % to 8.5 % was observed (**Figure A. 3**). This phase development indicated that part of the parent phase was irreversibly transformed into martensite by the cyclic mechanical stress.^[56,57] This retained martensite, especially when stabilized by dislocation structures or local inhomogeneities in the composition, may degrade the superelastic response and reduce the reversibility of the shape memory effect in service.^[58,59]

3.7 Metamaterial segments

Based on the highest recoverability observed in the previous section, process parameters used for the production of group C were chosen to produce metamaterial segments. Modulus of elasticity in FEA determined separately for each loading cycle was derived from compression test of the cylinders from the same group (**Figure 12**). This step was decided due to cyclic strain hardening behavior of nitinol reported in where tested specimens of metamaterials showed significantly higher stiffness than the numerical results for validation in 10th loading cycle.^[8] Figure 12 confirms these findings expressed in terms modulus of elasticity change with the most significant difference between 1st and 3rd cycle. All together the modulus of elasticity changed from 21.6 GPa to 28.5 GPa within 10 cycles. The values obtained were further used for parametrical computations described further in this section.

Figure 12 – Modulus of elasticity used in FEA of metamaterials segments at individual cycles.

Figure 13 (a)-(c) demonstrates a comparison of the force reaction of individual lattice structure segments. For each geometry the change in nominal wall thickness caused different reaction shift, where Figure 13 (a) shows nearly two times higher values when the wall thickness increased, while Figure 13 (c) tends to minimal changes. This was to some extent given by ratio of unit cells in vertical and horizontal direction, their size and arrangement in metamaterial

segment. However, all geometries tested in experiment had common trend of declining force in a range 2-4 % between the first and the tenth cycle. This trend appointed to phenomenon related to deterioration of recoverability previously observed for cylinders. Similar behavior was described by Yan et al. who investigated spatial metamaterials made of nitinol.^[8] In addition, irregular deformation distribution predicted by FEA and validated by DIC (Figure 13 (d)) appoints to variation of loading history across specimens, which indicates continuous deterioration without early stabilization.

Comparison with simulation showed consistency across all computationally determined results indicating underestimation of metamaterial stiffness in the several first loops of cyclic loading. With increasing number of cycles, however prediction of force reaction got closer to the experimental results. This effect was attributed to changes in the loading history of material described for cylinders (Figure 7) from which the modulus of elasticity in FEA was derived. Changes manifested in narrowing hysteresis loops with increasing number of loading cycles where difference between loading and unloading pathways was nearly negligible. It allowed to use relatively simple material model definition with linear elastic assumption resulting in a good accuracy of prediction in a later stage of cyclic loading. On the other hand, based on diagrams in Figure 13 (a)-(c) can be concluded that initial performance in initial stages of cyclic loading required using sophisticated definition of material model like one proposed by Auricchio et al. where nonlinear definition loading and unloading pathways of hysteresis loop would fit better.^[4] It would however lead to higher computational efforts coming out of convergency issues induced by strong material nonlinearities.

Figure 13 – Peak force reaction of metamaterial segment under cyclic loading – experiment vs FEA for (a) re-entrant; (b) arrowhead; (c) honeycomb; (d) qualitative comparison for nominal wall thickness of 0.5 mm.

It should be noted that when designing components with a small number of load cycles, the simple material model used enables a good prediction of the behavior even for complex metamaterial structures. This approach may also be suitable for components in space applications with a known number of load cycles over the lifetime of the component. For instance, it could be used for the development of new separation systems for small satellites with limited dimensions and weight, where ensuring 100% functionality for a single payload separation is essential. Only a limited number of element-level tests (tens) and 2–3 qualification tests of the functional system are performed prior to launch. Despite the high degree of degradation of the recoverable strain (recovery ratio approx. 50 %), additively manufactured NiTi structures still offer very attractive values for the usable deformation (approx. 2.5 %) and thus provide an opportunity for weight reduction.

4. Conclusion

A wide range of L-PBF processing parameters were investigated for the production of a Ni_{50.7}Ti_{49.3} alloy, resulting in three series with excellent properties. In all three series, a relative porosity of less than 0.1% was achieved in the bulk specimens, with no macroscopic cracks present. The highest A_f transformation temperature measured was 14 °C, which clearly indicates a purely superelastic behavior at room temperature. The mechanical and microstructural properties of bulk material under cyclic loading and the prediction of recoverable strain for metamaterial structures were investigated with a view to future potential applications. The main results can be summarized as follows:

1. Different processing parameters led to different levels of recoverable strain, with an absolute difference of around 0.7 % within the groups studied.
2. During cyclic loading, the superelastic performance deteriorated considerably. The deterioration in recovery strain and the rapid change in the shape of the loading loop were most significant in the first 5 cycles. The observed trend of material deterioration stabilized on average after 30 cycles in the tested groups.
3. No plateau region for load loops was observed, with increasing number of load cycles the hysteresis tended to narrow to a quasilinear pseudoelasticity with almost no hysteresis.
4. The recoverable strain decreased with increasing load. From a recovery ratio of 53.4 % at intermediate load level of 800 MPa to 35.1 % at a high load level of 1200 MPa.
5. TKD after cyclic loading confirmed fine martensite laths embedded in deformation bands, indicating a high dislocation density. A significant decrease in B2 austenite phase fraction from 97.7 % to 91.5 % and an increase in B19' martensite from 2.3 % to 8.5 % was observed. The presence of residual martensite in these areas indicated a partial irreversibility of the transformation process.
6. Cyclic compression of metamaterial segments showed a decreasing tendency of force response in a range of 2-4 % between the first and the tenth cycle, according to the observations on bulk specimens. The irregular distribution of deformation across the structure predicted by FEA was confirmed by DIC.
7. Simulation of metamaterial segments using a simple material model and a variable modulus (21.6-28.5 GPa) allowed accurate prediction of the force response after more than 5 cycles, clearly distinguishing the effects of thickness and structure type.

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Declaration of interest statement

The authors report there are no competing interests to declare.

Data availability statement

The data that support the findings of this study are openly available in Zenodo repository at 10.5281/zenodo.14499514.

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Appendix

Figure A. 1 – Dependence of the single track (a) width; (b) depth; (c) height and (d) contact angle on the scanning speed and laser power.

Table A. 1 – Quadratic regression coefficients and intercept; MSE and R2 are the mean square error and coefficient of determination, respectively.

Quadratic regression								
Property	Intercept		Coefficients				MSE	R ²
	β_0	β_1	β_2	β_3	β_4	β_5		
Track width	1.61e2	-1.58e-1	1.05e0	3.49e-5	-9.12e-5	-1.03e-3	584.32	0.90
Track depth	5.79e1	-2.93e-1	2.26e0	8.88e-5	-4.28e-4	-2.48e-3	1940.1	0.85
Track height	3.72e1	1.90e-3	9.22e-2	-6.51e-7	-9.82e-6	-1.78e-4	128.27	0.05
Contact angle	1.35 e2	-3.12e-2	1.24e-1	6.63e-6	4.93e-6	-7.53e-5	154.35	0.29

– Quadratic regression coefficients and intercept; MSE and R² are the mean squared error and coefficient of determination, respectively

Figure A. 2 – Section of the window with the process parameters used for the preparation of the individual single tracks (red – discarded, orange – considered but discarded, green – used further).

Figure A. 3 – XRD pattern for specimen of group C in (a) as-built state; (b) after cyclic loading